

MEASUREMENT OF THE TEMPERATURE-DEPENDENT PERMITTIVITY OF LUNAR REGOLITH SIMULANTS VIA MICROWAVE HEATING.

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Introduction: Lunar regolith is a dielectric material which can be efficiently heated to melting temperature using microwave energy [1]. Sintered or melted regolith can then be used as feedstock to construct infrastructure on the Moon, including landing pads, roadways and habitats. Additionally, it can be used to produce more complex components using additive manufacturing.

A material's permittivity, (with the real part or dielectric constant ϵ' , and imaginary part or loss factor, ϵ''), is the factor governing the behaviour of materials under electromagnetic fields, and thus, determining the efficiency of microwave heating. For lunar regolith, permittivity increases with temperature [2].

Temperature-dependent measurements of permittivity in lunar regolith simulants, up to their melting temperature, are crucial for enhancing computational models and increasing the accuracy of numerical simulations related to the microwave heating process. This will facilitate improved modelling for the design and optimisation of regolith melting using microwave heating.

Dynamic measurement of dielectric properties: In this study, a dual-mode technique was employed to enable simultaneous measurement of real and imaginary permittivity of lunar regolith simulants while heating approximately 2g samples with 150W microwave power close to 2.43GHz [3]. The mare simulant JSC-1A and highland simulant NU-LHT-4M were heated from ambient temperature to melting temperature at a rate of 0.25°C/s under a nitrogen gas environment. Rapid changes in permittivity were measured instantaneously, with permittivity calculated using an enhanced Cavity Perturbation Method [3].

Temperature dependent permittivity: The real and imaginary permittivity of lunar regolith simulants were found to increase significantly with regolith simulant temperature for both mare and highland simulants, shown in Figures 1 and 2.

For both simulants, permittivity increases gradually at lower temperatures. However, near the glass transition temperature, T_g , the rate increases more rapidly, with NU-LHT-4M exhibiting a particularly sharp increase. A further rapid increase in permittivity occurs close to the onset of melting, T_m , of the material.

From ambient temperature up to approximately 750°C, the results of this study align with previous

datasets obtained using resistance furnace heating [2,5]. However, above 750°C, permittivity is notably higher under microwave heating compared to resistance furnace heating, particularly for the highland simulant, with both JSC-1A and NU-LHT-4M simulants efficiently heated to melting temperature using microwave energy.

Figure 1: Real and imaginary permittivity of JSC-1A as a function of temperature, microwave heating. T_g and T_m are from [4].

Figure 2: Real and imaginary permittivity of NU-LHT-4M as a function of temperature, microwave heating. T_g and T_m for NU-LHT-5M are shown [5] due to the absence of available data for NU-LHT-4M. However, since both simulants are part of the same simulant series and manufactured from the same feedstock, these properties are expected to be similar.

Discussion: Under microwave heating, the heterogeneous composition of regolith simulants, with a mixture of crystalline and glass components, each with different dielectric and thermal properties, leads to differential heating at a microscale. In powdered materials, the electric field can concentrate on the contact points between particles, further amplifying localised heating [6].

The low thermal conductivity of regolith simulants prevents uniform heat distribution, resulting in

significant temperature gradients, particularly at high temperatures. As the permittivity of regolith simulants increases with temperature, preferential absorption of microwave energy in these hotspots accelerates the heating further, which can result in thermal runaway. This highlights the importance of selecting an appropriate heating rate to ensure uniform heating throughout the sample volume and minimise the formation of localised hotspots.

Terrestrial feedstocks used to produce lunar regolith simulants contain non-lunar phases, such as hydrates, carbonates, sulphates and clays, which release volatile gases on heating [7]. When heated to melting temperature, returned regolith samples from mare and highland regions also exhibited outgassing due to chemical reactions between regolith constituents, and from gas-rich inclusions formed during the solidification of the original magma [8]. In our study, optical microscopy indicated that the outer layer of the post-heated material was characterised by vesicles, with a larger void at the core of the sample. The release of gases, coupled with the viscous flow of the glass phase through the material as the temperature increases, can lead to modifications in the sample geometry. Therefore, further studies are planned to investigate the application of low pressure as a means to facilitate gas release from the sample.

The variations in temperature-dependent dielectric values observed as a function of the heating mechanism (resistance furnace heating or microwave) are consistent with previous studies. These differences may be attributed to enhanced charge mobility under microwave heating, which recent studies suggest is the primary mechanism responsible for the increased dielectric properties compared to resistance heating [9].

Conclusions: This study provides valuable insight into the temperature-dependent dielectric properties of lunar regolith under microwave heating. Incorporating temperature-dependent permittivity across the entire heating range will improve the accuracy of numerical simulations of microwave heating of lunar regolith. Future work will focus on enhancing the existing COMSOL model [10] by incorporating the temperature dependent permittivity measurements from this study.

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